

Flexible Solutions for Industrial Use

UNICO₂RN develops modular and adaptable systems to suit different industrial needs and applications, as well as varying qualities of biogenic CO₂. A key feature is the successful demonstration of these technologies at two industrial sites operating at near-commercial conditions.

These demonstrations focus on producing microbial proteins, serving as sustainable nutrition for food and animal feed, and biodegradable bioplastics called polyhydroxyalkanoates, which can replace conventional plastics.

By validating these solutions at Technology Readiness Level 7, UNICO₂RN paves the way for broader adoption across industries.

Commitment to Safety and Sustainability

Beyond technical innovations, UNICO₂RN undertakes extensive safety and sustainability assessments. The project evaluates environmental, social, and economic impacts while ensuring compliance with future EU certification frameworks for sustainability.

This approach guarantees a safe and responsible scale-up of the technology, reinforcing its positive contributions towards lowering greenhouse gas emissions and supporting a circular bioeconomy.

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Consortium

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Project Details

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unicor2rn.eu

UNICO₂RN

Flexible and Efficient Capture and Bioconversion of CO₂ to Materials and Ingredients

Turning Biogenic CO₂ into Valuable Products

The UNICO₂RN project tackles one of today's most pressing challenges: carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions contributing to climate change. It targets CO₂ from biological sources such as biomass and organic waste.

By capturing this biogenic CO₂ and transforming it through cutting-edge technology, UNICO₂RN creates valuable ingredients and materials that support a circular economy.

The project combines two innovative approaches:

- 1 An advanced metal-organic-framework (MOF) based technology for efficient CO₂ capture and purification, and
- 2 specialised hydrogen-oxidising bacteria that convert captured CO₂ into useful compounds.

Together, these approaches offer a viable alternative to fossil-based production methods.

Sampling and collection of biogenic CO₂ point sources

CO₂ separation

Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOF) based CO₂ capture

CO₂

UNICO₂RN Benefits

- Effective capture and purification of biogenic CO₂
- Sustainable conversion into microbial proteins and biodegradable bioplastics (80% energy efficiency gains)
- Modular technology adaptable to diverse industrial settings and needs
- Validation at near-commercial scale under real conditions
- Significant reduction in greenhouse gas emissions (minimum 75% reduction)
- Comprehensive safety and sustainability assessments aligned with EU frameworks
- Safer than current methods (operation at mild temperature and pressure, no solvents or use of green extraction solvents)
- Enhanced stakeholder engagement to support market uptake

Engaging Stakeholders for Impact

UNICO₂RN actively involves a broad spectrum of stakeholders, including application users, researchers, industry, and policymakers.

Through clear communication and targeted dissemination, the project fosters awareness, acceptance, and uptake of carbon capture and utilisation technologies.

This engagement strategy helps build a strong foundation for market integration and highlights the environmental and societal benefits of transforming biogenic CO₂ into valuable products.